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The Level of Business Activity in Russian Industry and the Potential for Enhancing Technological Independence of Enterprises in the Context of Digital Transformation

KEYWORDS

business level activity,
Russian industry,
technological independence enhancement,
digital transformation,
economic development

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of the study stems from the fact that, despite the challenging economic and political situation in Russia affecting both industry and the economy as a whole, issues have arisen not only with the supply of foreign raw materials and goods to the Russian market but also with ensuring the uninterrupted operation of domestic industry. Under these conditions, it is necessary to develop and formulate new, more effective approaches to the strategy for the development of Russian industry amid forced modernization of the sector. It is also important to identify the factors that have the greatest and least impact on the business activity of industrial enterprises.

The study is aimed at determining the level of business activity in Russian industry and analyzing opportunities for enhancing the technological independence of enterprises through the implementation of digital transformation.

Materials and methods. The study draws on articles from authoritative academic journals. It employs statistical data reflecting the dynamics of the business confidence index among industrial enterprises, as well as indicators exerting a negative influence on the growth of Russian industrial production.

Results. New directions for the effective development of Russian industry are proposed based on an assessment of the business confidence index in extractive and manufacturing enterprises. The level of business activity among industrial enterprises, particularly in extractive and manufacturing sectors, exhibits volatile fluctuations. The study identifies factors negatively affecting the development of industrial production.

Conclusion. The study demonstrates that achieving the strategic goal – transitioning Russian industrial sector to an innovative development path – requires the adoption of advanced technologies, scientific developments, and enterprise modernization. Amid sanctions, a key challenge is maintaining economic resilience and boosting innovation activity, which calls for theoretical and practical measures, as well as government support to enhance industrial stability.

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INTRODUCTION

The study of business activity in Russian industry is highly relevant, as its analysis helps assess current industrial trends and identify growth or decline in production, which directly impacts the country's economic stability and development. Furthermore, examining business activity is crucial for corporate leaders and government authorities who rely on industrial data to formulate strategies, investment plans, and sectoral support policies.

Analyzing current indicators enables forecasts for industrial and broader economic development, a critical aspect in shaping long-term strategies. Understanding the real state of Russian industry facilitates more effective participation in global value chains and helps build competitive advantages in the international arena.

The industrial business activity index serves as a foundation for evaluating the condition of various sectors and regions, given that industry supplies tools, raw materials, and other essential resources. Key metrics in assessing the financial health of Russian industrial enterprises include risk resilience, business activity levels, and other parameters. Experts analyzing the current state and innovative development pathways through new technology adoption argue that research in this field remains insufficient and exists mostly as theoretical frameworks with limited practical applications.

Despite the challenging economic and political environment facing Russian industry and the economy at large, issues have emerged not only with the supply of foreign raw materials and goods to the Russian market, disrupting uninterrupted enterprise operations, but also with the need to develop new, more robust approaches to industrial strategy amid forced modernization. Notably, a positive annual trend in risk resilience indicators has gained significance, demonstrating that sectors such as automotive and electrical equipment manufacturing have achieved certain successes in maintaining stability [1].

Recent studies, conducted under sanctions and restrictions, have significantly influenced the development of metrics that most accurately reflect the level of industrial production and its actors in the country [2]. The business confidence index stands out as a leading indicator, capturing industry's role in shaping an efficient economic space and regional processes toward building effective regional economies.

Thus, the relevance of this study stems from the fact that, despite Russia's complex economic and political landscape affecting both industry and the broader economy, challenges have arisen not only in securing foreign raw materials and goods critical for industrial continuity but also in the urgent need to devise more substantial approaches to industrial development strategy under forced modernization. The research also aims to identify the factors exerting the greatest and least influence on industrial business activity, along with defining its objectives.

The study is aimed at determining the level of business activity of the Russian industry and analyzing the possibilities of increasing the technological independence of enterprises through the implementation of digital transformation.

METHODS

The study utilized articles from authoritative periodicals including Regional Research of Russia, Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, Studies on Russian Economic Development, Steel in Translation, Scientific and Technical Information Processing, Advances in Science, Technology & Innovation, Russian Engineering Research, and others.

The research employs statistical data on the dynamics of the industrial business confidence index, along with factors negatively affecting the growth of Russian industrial production.

A systems analysis approach was adopted as the research method. This enables examination of contemporary economic processes while accounting for both positive and negative factors influencing industrial development within regional systems.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sanctions adversely affect Russian industrial business activity by restricting access to technologies, investments, and foreign markets, thereby slowing development and reducing sectoral competitiveness.

M. Y. Malkina analyzes industrial growth rates and drivers across Russian regions during the 2022-2023 imposition of new anti-Russian sanctions. The author reveals significant interregional disparities in industrial growth rates across key sectors during both stagnation (2022) and moderate growth (2023) periods. Over two years, industrial growth ranged from -26.8% in Kaliningrad Oblast to +38.3% in Bryansk

Oblast. The study identifies statistically significant positive effects of human capital quality and telecommunications sector share in regional GDP on industrial growth in both 2022 and 2023, alongside negative impacts from economic openness (measured through import dependence, exports, and foreign investments), though these factors' significance varied temporally [3].

R. Viktoriia examines commodity sector in Russia considering post-pandemic Western sanction policy changes. The author concludes that diversification has reduced Russia's resource dependence. Analysis of metallurgical sector enterprises demonstrates varying levels of real-world innovative activity, with implemented transformations facilitating adaptation [4].

E.K. Chirkunova and I.V. Kallin examined current trends in Russian oil industry during 2022-2023, analyzing financial performance of major global oil and gas companies. The study identified key challenges stemming from sanctions, particularly the need to establish new partnerships with Asian markets. The authors systematized emerging trends in oil industry development in relation to global economic transformations, while proposing additional government support measures including logistics development, improved access to financing and insurance, and support for deep processing projects and domestic oilfield services technologies [5].

N.V. Galtseva highlighted how the 2022 sanctions package significantly impacted Russia's gold mining industry, which relies heavily on imported high-performance equipment and global markets. The study analyzed factors increasing production costs and depressing gold prices [6].

S.L. Usnyan investigated foreign automobile production in Russia amid geopolitical constraints, economic uncertainty, and COVID-19. The research revealed a dramatic decline in automotive production during 2020, with domestic manufacturers accounting for less than 50% of market share, while identifying potential for expanded cooperation with Southeast Asian automakers [7].

D.B. Kuvalin et al. analyzed challenges facing Russian corporations due to Western sanctions, including tax burden issues, while documenting corporate perspectives on energy efficiency and climate adaptation [8].

Digitalization was shown to enhance industrial business activity through process automation, improved management, and increased competitiveness.

A. A. Kurochkina et al. examine pandemic-induced transformations in Russian business, identifying key digitalization trends among domestic companies. The

researchers reveal global digitalization patterns and distinctive features of digital transformation in Russian enterprises. The authors conclude that business digital transformation through crowdsourced business process modeling systems is essential to meet modern economic requirements [9].

O. Smirnova and L. Chesnyukova investigate how digitalization impacts technological development in Russian industry to achieve technological sovereignty. The scholars present a theoretical model of industrial technological development comprising five key components: innovation and investment, digital transformation, education and human resources, environmental sustainability, and government support [10].

M. Plakhotnikova et al. argue that current metallurgical industry conditions necessitate improved approaches to digital transformation. The researchers contend that implementing digital technologies for metallurgical business processes should leverage the sector's existing potential, particularly its innovative capacity. The study emphasizes the need to identify and address critical barriers impeding digital transformation in metallurgy [11].

O. A. Romanova and D. V. Sirotin posit that transitioning Russian economy to new technological foundations meeting not just Industry 4.0 standards but broader criteria, represents the only viable path to technological sovereignty. Their analysis of development trends in Russian metallurgy reveals growing environmental and social responsibility requirements while establishing technological and organizational benchmarks for future progress [12].

I. Somina and A. Falko examine key aspects of digital transformation in business processes within the construction and transportation sectors. Their research identifies that construction organizations most actively utilize digital technologies (broadband internet, cloud services) and software systems (electronic document management systems, legal reference systems) [13].

The same researchers have identified the most digitally progressive sectors of the entrepreneurial economy: telecommunications, information technology, manufacturing, mining, energy supply, construction, as well as water supply, wastewater management, and waste disposal. The authors demonstrate a strong correlation between levels of digital and innovative development across these industries [14].

P. Ogorodnikov et al. analyze external and internal growth factors of agricultural-industrial complex (AIC) in Russia. The study presents successful case studies of Russian

digital platforms and services implemented in AIC enterprises. The researchers conclude that digital transformation of AIC through robotics and production automation systems should enhance all operational aspects of agricultural enterprises, collectively leading to significant improvements in labor productivity, decision-making quality, and ultimately regional economic efficiency [15].

S. Bondarkov et al. highlight how Russian businesses face new digital challenges and threats under current geopolitical conditions. This necessitates flexible approaches and innovative solutions to strengthen domestic capabilities in information security. The authors assess the current state of cybersecurity in industrial businesses and explore potential measures to restore stability while ensuring effective public-private cooperation in this domain [16].

O.V. Siunturenko emphasizes the critical importance of developing Russian economy through new industrialization. The study examines objectives and challenges of information support for reindustrialization across various stages: import substitution, military production conversion, development of high-tech industrial segments, and improving information resource utilization for domestic scientific and production sectors [17].

Innovative approaches to enhancing business activity in Russian industry include implementation of digital technologies, adoption of smart manufacturing systems, development of eco-friendly and energy-efficient solutions, formation of innovation clusters and partnerships.

A.M. Kalinin analyzes 2022 outcomes regarding investment dynamics determinants. The study evaluates investment activity factors from business perspectives, finding that even significant institutional environment deterioration does not immediately affect investment activity. Transportation, logistics, and wholesale trade sectors demonstrated notable flexibility and investment readiness despite uncertainty. Key investment drivers included resource availability (particularly credit resources), confirmed solvent demand, and technological dependencies across Russian industries [18].

D.B. Kuvalin et al. present corporate perspectives on impact of Western sanctions. The research reveals substantial expansion of current investment activity and intensification of investment plans among enterprises. Findings include growing ESG awareness among Russian businesses alongside decreasing ESG priority under sanctions [19].

S.V. Terebova and S.L. Ivanov define critically low innovation activity indicators, signaling systemic problems requiring identification and solution development.

The authors examine distinctive innovation behaviors among small, medium, and large industrial enterprises within regional contexts, particularly regarding barriers to innovation enhancement [20].

A. A. Goryushkin and S. R. Khalimova analyze the state and development of high-tech business at the regional level in relation to the economic complexity of regional economies. The authors identify key technological development directions: connected diversification of sectors aimed at increasing their share in the value chain with growing added value; technological modernization to enhance competitiveness of export-oriented products; innovation breakthrough – creation of high-tech and knowledge-intensive industries producing high value-added goods in regions with major mining corporations; and smart specialization involving development of local advantages, market expansion, and interregional cooperation [21].

I. A. Toymentseva et al. examine issues of innovative development in Russian industrial production, identifying priority economic sectors, proposing a classification of industrial innovation directions, assessing innovation activity in leading countries, and analyzing growth rates of innovation expenditures across economic sectors. The authors argue that despite significant innovation investments, their effectiveness remains extremely low, partly due to the lack of conditions for practical implementation of scientific developments [22].

T. Tagaeva et al. note that non-energy industrial enterprises, unlike energy companies, represent an economic sector where decarbonization is significantly more labor-intensive and risky under Russia's experimental emissions trading system launched in 2021. The authors conduct comparative analysis of decarbonization strategies between "Iskitimcement" (Novosibirsk region, Russia) and "Aalborg Portland" (Denmark) cement plants, revealing substantial gaps in carbon intensity between Russian and international benchmarks [23].

O. A. Rodionova et al. present structural analysis of business activity among agricultural value chain participants. The authors propose a methodological approach to assess adaptive capacity of agribusiness entities based on financial and economic indicators reflecting development sustainability considering regional specifics, with particular focus on project-based transformation in agriculture and other AIC sectors [24].

N. A. Kazakova and V. G. Kogdenko analyze an indicator system for monitoring chemical industry transformation processes. Their institutional evaluation approach

groups enterprises by criteria of maximum revenue growth contribution, net investment patterns, and business behavior models [25].

A. S. Zinchenko argues that despite specific technical and regulatory characteristics of oil and gas enterprises, the Running Lean concept based on hypothesis testing and continuous business model adaptation proves effective for operational optimization. The author emphasizes that adapting Running Lean to oil and gas requires collaboration with industry-specific experts [26].

K. K. Furmanov and Y. V. Turovets present results assessing impact of 2022 events on Russian manufacturing output volumes. The researchers identify six industry groups by predicted shock effects (from extremely negative to moderately positive), showing most sectors experienced significant negative impacts, particularly intermediate goods producers and certain machinery industries [27].

S. Y. Solodovnikov et al. highlight how growing environmental problems and consumption intensification necessitate industrial modernization toward sustainable development. The authors develop classification criteria for circular business models, identifying four types focused on: long-lifecycle products, lifecycle extension, circular lifecycle creation, and eco-neutral product completion [28].

I. Avlasenko et al. note that contemporary Russia, while possessing certain competitive advantages, requires transformation of global economic relations shaped by scientific and technological progress. Strengthening Russia's global position through adoption of new technologies and creating favorable conditions for innovation-driven development represents a strategic priority. This approach would facilitate structural economic reforms to reduce resource dependence while accelerating qualitative economic growth, improving living standards, and enhancing national technological security [29].

The reviewed literature demonstrates that numerous scholars have examined various aspects of impact of sanctions and external factors on Russia's economy during 2022-2023. Research confirms that sanctions have significantly affected multiple sectors of Russia's economy, necessitating development of adaptive solutions and establishment of new partnerships.

The analysis of studies on digitalization and technological development across Russian economic sectors reveals several key findings. Scholars identify critical digital transformation trends, particularly the need for advanced business process modeling systems. Enhancing industrial technological sovereignty through innovation ecosystems, strategic investments, and sustainable development solutions emerges

as a consistent theme. Sector-specific research highlights priority areas including digital modernization in metallurgy, smart technologies in construction, precision agriculture in agribusiness, cybersecurity infrastructure development. The collective findings underscore the imperative for Russian industries to develop adaptive capabilities amid global competition and geopolitical volatility, with particular emphasis on technological diversification, import substitution strategies, regional industrial cluster development.

RESULTS

The assessment of business activity in industrial enterprises and the economic evaluation of their innovation potential have become particularly relevant issues today. This study examined key indicators including the business confidence index and levels of business activity in both extractive and manufacturing industries. Analysis reveals that manufacturing sectors demonstrate more positive trends in these indices compared to extractive industries. This favorable performance in manufacturing is attributable to stable demand levels maintained throughout the recent period and strong production output expectations for upcoming periods (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Dynamics of the business confidence index in industrial enterprises, (%) [30]

The data presented in Fig. 1 show that the index for manufacturing industries remained unchanged from the previous year. An increase in the proportion of managers reporting growth in current product demand (up to 12.5%) was offset by a decline in production outlook expectations for the next three months (from 27.2% to 26.5%). Positive dynamics in the business confidence index are observed in manufacturing – one of the most innovative industrial sectors. The extractive industry also demonstrates positive trends, though to a lesser extent compared to manufacturing. This situation necessitates an assessment of the key factors influencing the positive development of Russian industrial production amid challenging economic and political conditions. The primary factor negatively impacting the Russian industrial sector is economic uncertainty. Other constraining factors include competitive imports and insufficient internal financing (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Level of factors negatively affecting the growth of Russian industrial production, (%) [30]

The survey revealed significant improvement in participants' sentiment and notable growth in key industrial indicators (demand-output) during the first three months of the current year. This emerging trend creates more favorable conditions for manufacturing enterprises compared to extractive industries. Russia's contemporary economy is currently developing models and mechanisms to enhance effective development through strategic innovation management as a driver for sustainable growth in regional economic systems. This reflects the need for further refinement and identification of optimal development pathways for Russian economic entities and regional systems. Researchers have consequently refined theoretical frameworks concerning strategic innovation management as a factor in sustainable regional economic development, emphasizing balanced growth principles. These approaches are fundamentally based on innovative directions that facilitate sustainable development achievement.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The strategic goal of transitioning Russia's industrial sector to an innovative development path can only be achieved through the implementation of advanced technologies, the utilization of scientific and technical developments, intellectual property assets, and the modernization of enterprises' material base. This study has identified the key factors that most significantly influence the development of Russian industry, particularly in the extractive and manufacturing sectors. The research highlights the need to reorient innovative industrial production processes toward alternative suppliers. However, achieving comparable product quality at competitive costs in the short term remains a considerable challenge. Among the dominant factors affecting both extractive and manufacturing industries, price increases stand out. The findings clearly indicate that current production capacities fully meet product demand. Under sanctions and restrictions, the government faces a critical task: not only maintaining the economic stability of the country and its regions from a national security perspective but also boosting innovation activity in industry. Thus, the study underscores the necessity of transforming innovation into a key driver of industrial resilience, which requires both theoretical and methodological groundwork as well as practical solutions derived from it. Undoubtedly, state support for the industrial sector is essential under the current circumstances.

REFERENCES

1. Aukutsionek, S. P. (2023). Economic situation in industry in the first half of 2023. *Economic development of Russia*, 9(30), 28–32.
2. Grebenkin, I. V. (2020). Trends in Changes in Industrial Specialization and Development Dynamics of Russian Regions. *Regional Economy*, 1(16), 69–83.
3. Malkina, M. Y. (2025). Industry of Russian Regions under New Anti-Russian Sanctions. *Regional Research of Russia*, 15, 41–56. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970524600793>
4. Viktoriia, R. (2023). Development of the Raw Material Sector of the Russian Industry in the Post-covid and Sanctions Period. In: Karabegovic, I., Kovačević, A., Mandzuka, S. (eds) *New Technologies, Development and Application VI. NT 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 707. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-34721-4_55
5. Chirkunova, E. K., & Kallin, I. V. (2024). Current Trends in the Development of Russian Oil Industry Enterprises: Regional Profile. In: Mantulenko, V. (eds) *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference Engineering Innovations and Sustainable Development. CEISD 2024. Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, vol 540. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-67372-6_41
6. Galtseva, N. V. (2023). The Gold Mining Industry of Magadan Oblast under Sanctions: Risks for the Region. *Regional Research of Russia*, 13, 490–495. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970523700788>
7. Usnyan, S. L. (2023). International Production in the Russian Automotive Industry. In: Popkova, E. G. (eds) *Sustainable Development Risks and Risk Management. Advances in Science, Technology & Innovation*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-34256-1_73
8. Kuvalin, D. B., Zinchenko, Y. V., & Lavrinenko, P. A. et al. (2025). Russian Enterprises at the End of 2024: Aggravation of Problems in the Context of Foreign Economic Sanctions and a High Key Interest Rate. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 36, 416–429. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700725700145>
9. Kurochkina, A. A., Lukina, O. V., & Semenova, J. E. (2024). Prospects and Specifics of the Use of Digital Technologies in Modern Russian Business. In: Vasant, P., et al. *Intelligent Computing and Optimization. ICO 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 874. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-50887-5_18
10. Smirnova, O., & Chesnyukova, L. (2024). Impact of Digitalisation on the Technological Development of Industry: Russian Experience. In: Appolloni, A., Kumar, V., Kuzmin, E., Akberdina, V. (eds) *The Future of Industry. Lecture Notes in Information Systems and Organisation*, vol 70. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66801-2_36
11. Plakhotnikova, M., Anisimov, A., Grabsky, A., Scriabin, O., & Suslova, M. (2025). Current Concepts of Managing the Digital Transformation of the Metallurgical Industry. In: Skhvediani, A., Kulachinskaya, A., Mateeva Petrova, M. (eds) *Digital Transformation of Socio-Economic and Technical Systems: Theory and Practice. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 1309. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-85608-2_23
12. Romanova, O. A., & Sirotin, D. V. (2024). From Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0: Problems and Opportunities for the Metal Industry Development in Russia. *Steel in Translation*, 54, 120–126. <https://doi.org/10.3103/S0967091224700438>
13. Somina, I., & Falko, A. (2023). Analysis of the Parameters of Digitalization of Business Processes in the Construction and Transport Industry. In: Guda, A. (eds) *Networked Control Systems for Connected and Automated Vehicles. NN 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 509. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-11058-0_46
14. Somina, I., & Falko, A. (2023). Comparative and Correlation Analysis of the Parameters of Digitalization and Innovation Activity of Business and Transport Organizations. In: Guda, A. (eds) *Networked Control Systems for Connected and Automated Vehicles. NN 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 510. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-11051-1_62
15. Ogorodnikov, P., Guseva, E., Trubin, S., Hludeeva, M., & Kolovertnova, M. (2023). Digital Transformation of the Agricultural Industry: Tasks and Prospects of Digitalization of Russian Organizations. In: Beskopylny, A., Shamtsyan, M., Artiukh, V. (eds) *XV International Scientific*

- Conference "INTERAGROMASH 2022". *INTERAGROMASH 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 574. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21432-5_143
16. Grigoriev, D., & Manakhova, A. (2023). Russian Industrial Business in the New International Cybersecurity Agenda. In: Baykov, A., Zinovieva, E. (eds) *Digital International Relations*. Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-3467-6_1
 17. Siuntiuurenko, O. V. (2023). The Reindustrialization of the Russian Economy: Information Tasks and Resources. *Scientific and Technical Information Processing*, 50, 157–165. <https://doi.org/10.3103/S0147688223030048>
 18. Kalinin, A. M. (2024). Factors of Investment Activity in the Russian Economy: Conclusions 2022. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 35, 21–33. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700724010052>
 19. Kuvalin, D. B., Zinchenko, Y. V., & Ibragimov, S. S. et al. (2024). Russian Enterprises in the Spring of 2024: Significant Increase in Investment Activity under Sanctions. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 35, 909–919. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700724700448>
 20. Terebova, S. V., & Ivanov, S. L. (2025). Innovative Activity of Russian Industrial Enterprises in Modern Conditions: Problems, Specifics, Solutions. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 36, 430–439. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700725700157>
 21. Goryushkin, A. A., & Khalimova, S. R. (2023). High-Tech Business and Economic Complexity of Russian Regions. *Regional Research of Russia*, 13, 260–270. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970523700624>
 22. Toymentseva, I. A., Chichkina, V. D., Guseva, N. V., & Vasetskaya, E. S. (2025). Russian Industry Development Trends: Innovative Aspect. In: Mantulenko, V. (eds) *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference Engineering Innovations and Sustainable Development. CEISD 2025. Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, vol 648. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-92520-7_18
 23. Tagaeva, T. O., Gorbacheva, N. V., & Savina, A. I. (2024). Strategies for Decarbonization of Cement Industry Enterprises: Russian and International Benchmarks. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 35, 667–677. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700724700205>
 24. Rodionova, O. A., Truba, A. S., Eryukova, I. D., & Evsyukova, T. G. (2024). Assessment of Adaptation Activity of Agricultural Business Subjects in the Project-Based Approach. In: Popkova, E. G., Bogoviz, A. V., Sergi, B. S., Kaurova, O. V., Maloletko, A. N. (eds) *Sustainable Development of the Agrarian Economy Based on Digital Technologies and Smart Innovations. Advances in Science, Technology & Innovation*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-51272-8_23
 25. Kazakova, N. A., & Kogdenko, V. G. (2024). Assessing the Transformation of the Chemical Industry Based on an Institutional Approach and Sustainable Development Criteria. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 35, 707–715. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700724700242>
 26. Zinchenko, A. S. (2024). Analysis of Business Models at Russian Oil and Gas Enterprises by an Adapted Running Lean Method. *Russian Engineering Research*, 44, 410–413. <https://doi.org/10.3103/S1068798X24700072>
 27. Furmanov, K. K., & Turovets, Y. V. (2024). Assessing the Impact of External Shocks on the Development of the Manufacturing Industry. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 35, 697–706. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700724700230>
 28. Solodovnikov, S. Y., Serhiyevich, T. V., Ugolnikova, O. D., & Pastukhov, A. L. (2023). Circular Business Models in Industry. In: Rumyantseva, A., Anyigba, H., Sintsova, E., Vasilenko, N. (eds) *Finance, Economics, and Industry for Sustainable Development. NCSDESG 2022. Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-30498-9_4
 29. Avlasenko, I., Avlasenko, L., & Podkolzin, Y. (2023). Analysis and Evaluation of Innovation Activity of the Russian Economy. In: Beskopylny, A., Shamtsyan, M., Artiukh, V. (eds) *XV International Scientific Conference "INTERAGROMASH 2022". INTERAGROMASH 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 574. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21432-5_241

30. Rosstat: On industrial production in the first half of 2023. Available at: https://rosstat.gov.ru/storage/mediabank/67_27-09-2023.html (accessed 12 September 2024).
31. Guseva, M. N., Brikoshina, I. S., & Yashalova, N. N. (2023). Digital Business Ecosystems: Russian Experience. *Scientific and Technical Information Processing*, 50, 190–195. <https://doi.org/10.3103/S0147688223030061>
32. Kuvalin, D. B., Zinchenko, Y. V., & Lavrinenko, P. A. et al. (2024). Russian Enterprises in the Spring of 2023: Overcoming the Sanctions Crisis and Strengthening Investment Activity. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 35, 150–160. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700724010076>
33. Kogdenko, V. G., Kazakova, N. A., & Sanzharov, A. A. (2021). Monitoring the Implementation of the Strategy for Development of the Electronics Industry of the Russian Federation. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 32, 683–688. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700721060071>

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